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“James Paisible’s Instrumental Trios: A Thematic Catalogue”

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This article discusses the instrumental trios of James Paisible (c.1656-1721), an important and prolific French wind player and composer, resident in London for most of his career. It places them in the context of the French repertory of suites for two treble instruments and bass, and investigates the occasionally complex relationship with versions intended for other instrumental scorings. The accompanying thematic catalogue of 169 trios in the three main sources serves as a resource for further research.